

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

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ABSTRACT

In this document we report on the complete dataset of Task 5.2 (microbial carbon use efficiency - CUE) of the EnergyLink project. CUE has been measured in 8 experiments of crop diversification across Europe and can be analysed in several ways. Here, we shortly explain the concept, the methodology and finally present the dataset which is provided in accordance to data management rules.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP	Work Package
EU	European Union

1. Introduction

Microbial carbon use efficiency (CUE) is a physiological parameter that is acknowledged to play an important role for the cycling of carbon in soils. Almost all carbon substrates that reach the soil will, sooner or later, pass through microbes. In this task, CUE is defined as the efficiency by which microbes can use carbon sources to grow, expressed as the ratio of carbon allocated to biosynthesis and total carbon that was taken up. The higher this ratio, the more carbon remains in the soil and can contribute to stabilised soil organic matter. It is therefore considered important to understand which factors, in an agricultural context particularly management factors, can contribute to an increase in CUE.

Crop diversification, such as the inclusion of a cover crop into the crop rotation, is considered multi-beneficial in intensive agricultural systems. Also soil microbiomes might respond in multiple ways to a diversification of plant-derived C inputs. However, potential diversification effects on microbial physiology are poorly understood and their evaluation is a key task of the EnergyLink project.

Task 5.2 encompasses the measurement of bulk soil microbial CUE and all associated parameters of microbial activity and physiology in more than 200 samples that have been received from a total of eight diversification experiments spanning a pan-European gradient from Spain to Sweden (Lithuania in the East). Several of these experiments have been sampled twice in different seasons, to check for a potential seasonality of the crop diversification effect.

2. The ^{18}O method to assess Carbon Use Efficiency in bulk soils

The microbial carbon use efficiency (CUE) is defined as the share of C directed to microbial growth to total C metabolised, i.e. the sum of C directed to growth and respiration (Manzoni et al. 2012). In contrast to conventional ^{13}C -labelling methods where the C substrate added could affect microbial activity and metabolic efficiency, no additional C is added within the ^{18}O -labelling method and therefore it is a valuable method to determine the metabolic efficiency during decomposition of soil organic matter (Geyer et al. 2019).

Within the EJP SOIL project EnergyLink, the ^{18}O -labelling method to determine microbial CUE during soil organic matter decomposition was performed according to Spohn et al. (2016), with the same modifications described in Poeplau et al. (2019). Formulae and a more detailed description of the method can be retrieved from Schroeder et al. (2021). In the ^{18}O -labelling method, microbial growth is determined based on the incorporation of ^{18}O -labelled water into newly formed DNA (Schwartz 2007). Microbial respiration is measured by the increase in CO_2 concentration in the headspace atmosphere of a closed-chamber incubation vessel. During the ^{18}O -method different parameters are assessed: the microbial biomass C, microbial growth rate, microbial respiration rate, total amount of extractable DNA, and microbial turnover.

Figure 1: Basic principle of the ^{18}O -labelling method to assess microbial carbon use efficiency (CUE). Two aliquots of pre-incubated soil samples are prepared, where one aliquot is labelled with ^{18}O -water and the second aliquot represents the natural abundance (NA) signature. After 24 h incubation a gas sample is taken from the labelled sample in order to assess the respiration rate from the increase in CO_2 concentration. Labelled and non-labelled soil samples are directly frozen and stored at -80°C until DNA is extracted. From the isotopic signatures the incorporation of ^{18}O into newly formed DNA can be calculated and converted into microbial growth rate using a conversion factor f_{DNA} , i.e. the ratio of microbial biomass C to total DNA extracted. CUE is calculated as C directed to growth over the total C uptake. Figure adapted from EUROSOIL2020CONT-1943 - PO366.

3. The dataset

Table 1 gives an overview of the measured samples. A total of 223 samples were analysed. The ensemble of sites and sampling dates enables different ways to analyse the data. For example, on some sites, a double sampling (seasonality) was performed, on others not. Some sites included a diversification gradient (i.e. single to multiple species cover crops), others had only a diversified and a control treatment (Table 2). An overview on all CUE data in topsoil samples is given in Figure 1. Those results are used as a starting point for sample selection in task 5.3. The delay of D5.3 will be justified and a detailed delivery plan will be provided.

Table 1: Overview on number of samples analysed for ^{18}O -CUE per site and sampling. In total 223 samples were sampled and analysed.

Country	Site	Sampled treatments	Year	Season	Exact date	Sampling depth	n replicates	n total	Analysed for ^{18}O -CUE
Sweden	Mellby R0-8403	C; D	2022	spring	04.05.2022	0-20 cm	3	6	x
Sweden	Mellby R0-8403	C; D	2022	autumn	22.11.2022	0-20 cm	3	6	x
Lithuania	Lithuania	0; 2	2022	autumn	11.07.2022	0-20 cm	0: 1 2: 4	5	x
Netherlands	Clever Cover Cropping	fallow; VOR	2022	spring	04.04.2022	0-20 cm	5	10	x
Netherlands	Clever Cover Cropping	fallow; V; R; O; VO; VR; OR; VOR	2022	summer	23.08.2022	0-20 cm	5	40	x
Netherlands	Clever Cover Cropping	fallow; V; R; O; VO; VR; OR; VOR	2022	winter	12.12.2022	0-30 cm; 30-60 cm	5	80	top: x sub: x
Czech Republic	Prague Ruzyne	CT; SA; SA+F	2022	autumn	31.10.2022	0-20 cm	4	12	x
Austria	St. Florian	fallow; white lupine; aqua pro	2022	autumn	10.06.2022	0-20 cm	4	12	x
France	Lusignan	T1; T2; T5	2022	spring	21.04.2022	0-20 cm	4	12	x
France	Lusignan	T1; T2; T5	2023	winter	15.12.2023	0-20 cm	4	12	x
Slovenia	Vineyards Koper	BC; PG	2022	autumn	10.10.2022	0-20 cm	4	8	x
Slovenia	Vineyards Koper	BC; PG	2023	spring	19.04.2023	0-20 cm	4	8	x
Spain	Seville Benacazon	CT; MC	2022	autumn	30.11.2022	0-20 cm	CT: 2 MC: 4	6	x
Spain	Seville Benacazon	CT; MC	2023	spring	06.01.2023	0-20 cm	CT: 2 MC: 4	6	x

Sweden
Lithuania
Netherlands
Czech Republic
Austria
France
Slovenia
Spain

C: control; D: ryegrass
0: control; 2: mustard
fallow: control; V: vetch; O: oats; R: radish; VR: vetch+radish; OR: oats+radish; VO: vetch+oats; VOR: vetch+oats+radish
CT: control; SA: mustard; SA+F: mustard+buckwheat
fallow: control; white lupine: white lupine; aqua pro: phacelia+linseed+sunflower+bristle oat+niger+sorghum+safflower
T1: permanent cropland; T2: 3-year grassland+crop rotation; T5: permanent grassland
BC: control; PG: permanent grass cover
CT: control; MC: natural vegetation cover

Table 2: Overview on which sites are suitable for the various data analysis options.

Country	Diversification measure	European gradient	Diversification gradient	Seasonality	Depth
Sweden	cover crop	x		*	
Lithuania	cover crop	x			
Netherlands	cover crop	x	D	*	z
Czech Republic	cover crop	x	D		
Austria	cover crop	x	D		
France	ley farming	x	(D)	*	
Slovenia	vegetation stripes	x		*	
Spain	vegetation stripes	x		*	

Figure 2: Microbial carbon use efficiency (CUE) of control and diversified treatments at individual sites. Colours indicate samples taken at different calendar seasons.

The data was stored according to the data management plan.

CUE dataset

[EJP-EL DATA CUE WHC pH.xlsx](#)

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